

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

NLRP8 is activated by human papillomavirus 16.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We previously described silencing of NLRP2 by high risk HPV16. Here we report activation of NLRP8 by HPV16. NLRP8 likely recognizes the major capsid protein of HPV16 (L1) since HPV16 L1 capsid is sufficient to activate NLRP8.